

Trust as a component of psychosocial well-being

Tsvetelina Ivanova¹, Tanya Dimitrova⁴

1 Department of Medical Pedagogy, Faculty of Public Health, Medical University of Sofia, Sofia, Bulgaria

2 Department of Ophthalmology, University Hospital "St. John the Baptist", Sofia, Bulgaria

3 Surgery Clinic, University Hospital "Alexandrovska", Sofia, Bulgaria

4 Medical Ophthalmological Clinic Vistamed - Sofia, Sofia, Bulgaria

Corresponding author: Tsvetelina Ivanova (tz.ivanova@fz.mu-sofia.bg)

Received 4 February 2024 ♦ Accepted 20 February 2024 ♦ Published 2 July 2025

Citation: Ivanova T, Dimitrov T, Koychev A, Dimitrova T (2025) Trust as a component of psychosocial well-being. *Pharmacia* 72: 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.72.e120227>

Abstract

The coronavirus pandemic affects the lifestyle, mental and physical health of people, especially those at direct risk of becoming infected. Data were collected from 296 healthcare workers through anxiety, self-assessment physical and mental health questionnaire. The findings suggest significant socio-demographic differences in the perception of and response to official information and measures taken during the pandemic, highlighting the complexity of public attitudes towards authorities in managing the crisis.

Keywords

psychosocial well-being, trust, healthcare workers, mental health

Introduction

Psychosocial well-being is expressed in the presence of a confidant. Trust is a person's willingness to be vulnerable to the actions of another person, based on the expectation that this other person will perform some important action for the trustor, regardless of the trustor's ability to monitor or control the other person. Trust is based on vulnerability and is a state in which people (most often team members) are open to each other without worry, leaving no room for suspicion or fear of retaliation. Trust is an attitude that includes an interest in and respect for the communication and interaction partner; an awareness of the needs that can be met when interacting with the communication partner; emotions about the antecedents of their satisfaction and a positive emotional appraisal of the partner; relaxation in the interaction and a willingness to show goodwill toward the partner as well as to carry out actions toward a successful interaction with the partner (Mayer et al. 1995; Lencioni 2013; Melekhin 2015; Psyca-bi.net 2020a).

Trust is built in early childhood. During the first phase of human development, caregiving provides the infant with a sense of inner well-being and comfort that forms a sense of trust that basic needs will be met. By instilling trust and appreciation in others, we encourage them to empathize with our natural drive for well-being (Selye 1982; Stefanova-Bakracheva 2006).

A well-being index should consider confidence. People who experience greater subjective well-being are more trusting. Trust is one of the fundamental aspects of the social and psychological well-being of the individual and society, and it can be defined as confidence in the safety of the surrounding world and its inhabitants. Individuals who realize social acceptance (a component of social well-being) trust other people, think that others are capable of kindness, and believe that people can be hardworking, diligent, and industrious (Keyes 1998; Korostyleva 2001; Diener and Seligman 2004; Diener and Ryan 2009).

Trust is part of social integration and social functioning as a component of positive mental health. Mistrust is

a psychological response to stress and psychological trauma. Paranoid personality disorder is characterized by mistrust of difference, which is associated with the experience of adversity. Without trust in the therapist, the helping person cannot achieve his or her goals; therapy cannot be successful. Trust is important in all areas of social life (Uzunov 2000; NHS Health Scotland 2008; Zhang et al. 2008; Furnham 2013; Oddagipermarket 2019).

Trust is also linked to family well-being. Mutual trust between partners in the family, trust in oneself, in other people and in the world at large ensures self-realization in the marital- familial sphere by contributing to a relationship of empathy, compassion, and empathy that does not violate the degree of autonomy and authenticity of each partner. Trust contributes to relationship satisfaction in the family. Positive trusting relationships with family members appear to increase life satisfaction in married people compared to single people - single/unmarried, not living with an intimate partner, or divorced/separated. A considerable influence on happiness is the level of trust in one's family. Satisfaction with family life is characteristic of spouses in the period 6–12 years of living together, depending on the degree of trust between spouses. For young men with family "seniority" of 1 to 3 years trust, and fidelity are among the priorities in family life. It seems that people who maintain trusting relationships with their family members have higher life satisfaction and self-esteem than single people. Having a large family, more children, and having more trust in one's family increases life satisfaction and happiness. People who are more satisfied with their lives trust other people more. Happier and more satisfied people trust others more, believe other people are honest, and believe that others do not try to take advantage of them (Myers and Diener 1995; Diener et al. 2000; Korostyleva 2001; Kesebir and Diener 2008; Shaimuhametova 2010; Vinson and Ericson 2012; Luhmann et al. 2013; Zankova 2015; Bryuhov 2016; Brito et al. 2019).

Family trust is a predictor of non-specific trust in people from countries where self-focus is emphasized in socialization. Individual level of trust in people we know personally is a predictor of nonspecific trust in people from 49 nationalities, being a stronger predictor in countries where socialization emphasizes self-directedness rather than another directedness. Individual level of trust in people who are not part of the groups to which we belong is a predictor of non-specific trust in people of all forty-nine nationalities studied, being a stronger predictor in countries where socialization emphasizes self-directedness and politeness instead of practicality. People who have a common background, a shared value system, and a similar worldview are quicker to build and experience greater trust in each other (Stofur 2005; Jing and Bond 2015).

Trust is associated with friendship. Friends are people we like, with whom we have common interests and activities, who understand and emotionally support us, whom we can trust and with whom we feel comfortable. Friendships fulfil a need for help, a need for social support, and a need for common interests. In individualistic cultures, the absence of

interactions with friends and the lack of a trusted friend is more strongly associated with loneliness than in collectivistic cultures. More trusting people allow other people less social distance than less trusting people. Trust is necessary for better and more effective interpersonal relationships (Tolor et al. 1975; Argyle and Henderson 1989; Stofur 2005; Zhang et al. 2008; Lykes and Kimmelmeier 2014; Stanoeva 2015).

If trust in others greatly exceeds trust in oneself, susceptibility to outside influences increases amid doubt in one's abilities. Extreme, polar variants of trust expression lead to inadequate life activity and problems in self-realization. Increased trust in the external world is accompanied by a lack of criticality and low reflection, and insufficient trust in the world is expressed in suspiciousness, and a limited point of view. Lowered trust in self leads to low self-esteem and low aspirations, and increased trust in self can lead to self-sufficiency and withdrawal from the world. A sufficiently high trust in oneself, against a background of openness to the outside world, appears to be beneficial for both life activity and self-realization. Self-confidence helps in self-affirmation and self-realization (Myers and Diener 1995).

The loss of professional fulfilment is experienced as distrust. Distrust in the people one works with is among the social symptoms of burnout. Lack of trust and support among employees leads to low relationship satisfaction and vice versa – high satisfaction leads to increased trust and support in colleagues. Relationships are maintained based on honesty, openness, understanding, responsiveness, and appreciation of both personal and others' efforts. Teachers' performance increases when tension is absent in the work environment and trust is high in the team (Georgieva 2019). Trust is important for performance and job satisfaction. Police officers identify trust and the sense of belonging engendered by the support they receive from management as major factors in job satisfaction. Trust facilitates professional negotiation and bargaining (Rusinova-Hristova and Karastoyanov 2000; Stamatov and Minchev 2003; Zhang et al. 2008; Stanoeva 2015; Sheeba et al. 2018; Oddagipermarket 2019).

Interpersonal relationships at work, based on support and trust, provide greater access to additional resources, as well as enable an increased sense of belonging to the organization, stimulating active participation in achieving organizational goals. Within the organization, trust is an important predictor of cooperative behavior, organizational commitment, and employee loyalty. Supervisor-employee exchanges of trust, mutual valuing, respect, and loyalty lead to increased organizational commitment in employees (specifically nurses), reduced turnover in the workplace, lead to greater organizational effectiveness, and increased organizational citizenship behavior. Organizational citizenship behavior takes the form of altruism, kindness, helping colleagues, loyalty, etc., which is discretionary, voluntary, and not subject to formal reward, but contributes to the effective functioning of the organization and has positive consequences for the well-being of individuals, groups, organizations, and society.

Satisfaction with trust among colleagues increases the manifestation of organizational citizenship behavior, and

on the other hand, a work environment that promotes organizational citizenship behavior provides higher employee satisfaction, which influences the perception of interpersonal relationships as supportive and trusting. Satisfaction with support and trust among coworkers is associated with fewer conflictual relationships in the organization (Chen et al. 2008; Spitzmuller et al. 2008; Montani et al. 2012; Dolan et al. 2013; Stanoeva 2015; Sheeba et al. 2018; Oddagipermarket 2019).

Satisfaction with relationships between colleagues includes satisfaction with trust, support, and formal work relationships, with satisfaction with trust between colleagues being lowest for members of different professions. Satisfaction with supervisors and coworkers encompasses satisfaction with trusting relationships with them, support and feedback on task performance, and the quality and intensity of interpersonal relationships. The human relationship-oriented supervisor develops a relationship of mutual trust, acknowledges, and treats staff experiences with confidence, and supports them in coping with negative events and concerns (Radoslavova and Velichkov 2005; Cohrs et al. 2006; Martínez-Corts et al. 2011).

Trust in the team is based on interpersonal understanding, acceptance of others' perspectives, concern, and support; belief in everyone's honesty, competence, openness and commitment. When trust is built, members freely reveal and discuss their weaknesses, fears and failures, and approach each other respectfully. The satisfaction of trust between colleagues is linked to the team roles of Innovator, Implementer and Coordinator. Individuals displaying openness to experience, and high levels of personal initiative are more likely to develop close and trusting relationships with colleagues and supervisors than those who are introverted and avoid new experiences (Stofur 2005; Stanoeva 2015).

A survey of members of different professions revealed that satisfaction with trust among colleagues was expressed at a medium level in 61.5% of cases, followed by low satisfaction with trust among colleagues in 19.7% of cases and high satisfaction with trust among colleagues in 18.8% of cases. Satisfaction with trust among colleagues was higher for workers in the humanities' occupations than for workers in the technical occupations. This is supported by the finding that teachers' satisfaction with trust among colleagues is rather high at about 72% of the possible satisfaction threshold. Older workers and those with more seniority are more satisfied with trust among colleagues than the youngest workers and those with up to 5 years of seniority. When satisfaction with trust among colleagues increases, satisfaction with work relationships, satisfaction with support from colleagues and supervisors, satisfaction with supervisor's attitude toward tasks, satisfaction with a supervisor's attitude toward human relations, satisfaction with feedback at work also increases, i.e., trust is related to different types of satisfaction (Stanoeva 2015; Kriviradeva 2019).

Trust in other people, trust in institutions such as government, and trust in public services are indicators of well-being and quality of life. People who experience greater subjective well-being trust the government more. Re-

search in 150 countries shows that government corruption, as perceived by individuals and society, lowers income and trust in institutions, which reduces subjective well-being and life satisfaction, and this effect is stronger in Western countries. Before the introduction of the currency board in Bulgaria, distrust towards the national unit of payment was established, indicative of the disadvantages in the economic and political life of the country. In 2013, Bulgarians ranked 27th out of 28 European countries in trust in the political system and 26th in trust in the justice system, which means that they probably experience low well-being, and low satisfaction with life, as evidenced by the fact that joining the European Union in 2007 increased satisfaction with life in Bulgaria as trust in the European Union increased, with younger people, those in work and those who have completed secondary education being the most satisfied with life in Bulgaria after joining the European Union.

Greater trust in institutions such as parliament, political parties, the press, the courts and the church is positively correlated with greater happiness in life. A big influence on happiness is the level of trust in the press. Young people in Bulgaria prefer the Internet in terms of its function to inform, but it has relatively low trust. Television in Bulgaria retains its traditional leading role as an information medium, and the more its users are exposed to its information impact, the more trust in it grows, revealing the role of television news and briefings on the coronavirus pandemic in shaping the emotional experiences, attitudes, and expectations of Bulgarian citizens, thereby also affecting their well-being. Specific stressors accompanying the COVID-19 pandemic include possible mistrust of information provided by the government and other official bodies. On the other hand, the media in Bulgaria is perceived by Bulgarians as reporting mostly negative events, but this does not significantly affect the extent to which Bulgarians self-identify as happy and satisfied with life (Vinson and Ericson 2012; Mizova et al. 2014; Inter-Agency Standing Committee 2020).

Subjects and methods

During the coronavirus pandemic, a cross-sectional study was conducted from November 2020 to February 2021, and the data were collected online or through direct contact with the subjects. The selection criteria were adult Bulgarians (above 18 years old) and those working in the field of healthcare. Ethics statement Participation was voluntary. The study conformed to the general ethical principles outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki – World Medical Association, Inc. 2008.

Subjects

The sample consisted of 296 health workers with different professions – physiotherapists, doctors, speech therapists, nurses, psychotherapists, medical orderlies, dentists, and pharmacists. Their age varied from 23 to 60 years, the average age was 33.8 years, with a standard deviation of 10.8 years.

The women participating in the study outnumbered (81.1%, i.e., almost four-fifths of the subjects) men (18.9%). There were 164 surveyed health workers with an intimate partner (55.4%) and the same number did not have any children, but only 40 health professionals with an intimate partner did not have any children (24.4%). There were 132 surveyed health workers (44.6%) without an intimate partner and the same number of the subjects had children, but only eight of the health professionals without an intimate partner had children (6%). Most surveyed health professionals worked in large cities with more than 50,000 inhabitants ($N = 120$, 40.5%) and in the capital ($N = 104$, 35.1%). An equal proportion of the participants worked in medium-sized cities from 25,000 to 50,000 inhabitants and in small towns up to 25,000 inhabitants – 36 (12.2%) from each category.

About one-fifth of those surveyed ($N = 84$; 28.4%) were diagnosed with coronavirus, and most ($N = 212$, 71.6%) were not.

Data processing

Statistical processing was performed using the software JASP 0.14 (JASP Team 2020) applying descriptive statistics, verification of the normality of the distribution by Shapiro - Wilk coefficient, correlation analysis by Spearman correlation coefficient, and non-parametric methods of Mann-Whitney and Kruskal -Wallis for group comparisons. The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in the Mendeley Data Repository at <https://doi.org/10.17632/8kj87624sw.1>.

Results

A study of trust in official authorities during the coronavirus pandemic found that 250 Bulgarians (39.4%) did not trust information from official sources (e.g., the government), while 385 did (60.6%). More Bulgarians aged 28 to 35 than expected did not believe information from official sources ($\chi^2 (N = 635; df = 3) = 32.483; p < 0.001$; Cramer's $V = 0.226$, indicating a small effect size or a medium effect size according to another interpretation (Goev 1996).

Table 1. Differences between age groups in their confidence in information provided by official sources during the coronavirus pandemic.

			Do you trust the information from official sources (e.g., government)?	
			No	Yes
Age groups	20–23	Observed values	81	108
		Expected values	74.4	114.6
	24–27	Observed values	41	98
		Expected values	54.7	84.3
	28–35	Observed values	84	66
		Expected values	59.1	90.9
	36–65	Observed values	44	113
		Expected values	61.8	95.2

However, only 95 Bulgarians (15%) surveyed stated that they considered the coronavirus situation to be a hoax (in the 28–35 age group, the coronavirus situation was perceived as a hoax significantly more often than expected than in other age groups), and the remaining 540 Bulgarians surveyed (85%) did not consider reports of coronavirus illness or the severity of coronavirus illness to be a hoax.

Table 2. Compared frequency distributions of age groups' responses on the perception of the coronavirus situation as a hoax.

		$\chi^2(N = 635; df = 3) = 31.922, p < 0.001$; Cramér's $V = 0.224$, i.e. moderate effect size, variables are moderately related		Do you believe the coronavirus situation is a hoax?	
				Yes	No
Age groups	20–23	Observed values		20	169
		Expected values		28.3	160.7
	24–27	Observed values		14	125
		Expected values		20.8	118.2
	28–35	Observed values		44	106
		Expected values		22.4	127.6
	36–65	Observed values		17	140
		Expected values		23.5	133.5

160 Bulgarians (25.2%) define illegitimate, and illegal the actions of the authorities regarding the self-isolation regime, while 475 Bulgarians (74.8%) consider them legitimate, and legal. Significantly more men than expected compared to women consider the actions of the authorities regarding the self-isolation regime as illegitimate, illegal ($\chi^2 (N = 635; df = 1) = 7.559; p = 0.006$; Cramer's $V = 0.109$, indicating a small effect size).

Table 3. Gender differences regarding the acceptance as legitimate of the authorities' actions on the self-isolation regime during the coronavirus pandemic.

		Are the authorities' actions regarding the self-isolation regime legitimate?	
		No	Yes
men	Observed values	74	162
	Expected values	59.5	176.5
women	Observed values	86	313
	Expected values	100.5	298.5

Significantly more Bulgarians aged between 28 and 35 than expected consider the authorities' actions regarding the self-isolation regime as illegitimate compared to other age groups ($\chi^2 (N = 635; df = 3) = 16.283; p = 0.001$; Cramer's $V = 0.160$, indicating a small effect size).

225 Bulgarians (35.4%) consider that the measures taken by the authorities regarding quarantine and self-isolation are not sufficient, while 410 Bulgarians (64.6%) consider these measures sufficient. Significantly more people with an intimate partner than expected considered the measures taken by the authorities on quarantine and self-isolation sufficient, and significantly more people without an intimate partner than expected considered them insufficient ($\chi^2 (N = 635; df = 1) = 15.439; p < 0.001$;

Table 4. Differences between age groups in their acceptance as legitimate of the authorities' actions regarding the self-isolation regime during the coronavirus pandemic.

			Are the authorities' actions regarding the self-isolation regime legitimate?	
			No	Yes
Age groups	20–23	Observed values	41	148
		Expected values	47.6	141.4
	24–27	Observed values	26	113
		Expected values	35.0	104.0
	28–35	Observed values	56	94
		Expected values	37.8	112.2
	36–65	Observed values	37	120
		Expected values	39.6	117.4

Cramer's $V = 0.156$, indicating a small effect size. People with an intimate partner do not always live in the same household as them and, with measures of social distance and self-isolation imposed, find it difficult to maintain their relationship, which is associated with a reluctance to have these measures continued or exacerbated.

In an earlier survey conducted from 25 April to 2 May 2020 among 868 Bulgarians, they rated safety measures to avoid coronavirus infection with an average score of about 7 on a scale from 1-totally inadequate to 10-totally adequate (Institute for Population and Human Studies 2020).

Table 5. Differences between people with and without an intimate partner in their acceptance of measures taken by the authorities on quarantine and self-isolation as sufficient.

		Are the measures taken by the authorities regarding quarantine, and self-isolation sufficient?	
		No	Yes
Without intimate partner	Observed values	122	156
	Expected values	98.5	179.5
With intimate partner	Observed values	103	254
	Expected values	126.5	230.5

60 people (9.4%) considered that these measures were introduced too early. According to 342 (53.9%), they were introduced just in time. According to 233 (36.7%), they were introduced too late. Significantly more people without children than expected thought these measures were introduced too late, and significantly more people with children than expected thought they were introduced just in time (χ^2 (N = 635; df = 2) = 66.559; $p < 0.001$; Cramer's $V = 0.324$, indicating a medium effect size).

Official announcements and rules angered 329 Bulgarians (51.8%), while the remaining 306 (48.2%) were not angered by official announcements and rules during the coronavirus pandemic. Experiencing anger was associated with deterioration in emotional well-being because of information from authorities during the coronavirus pandemic. Significantly more women than expected than men were angered by official announcements and rules during

the coronavirus pandemic (χ^2 (N = 635; df = 1) = 5.857; $p = 0.016$; Cramer's $V = 0.096$, indicating a small effect size).

Table 6. Differences between surveyed Bulgarians without and with children in their opinion on how timely the measures taken by the authorities during the coronavirus pandemic were introduced.

			Were these measures implemented:		
			Too early	Just in time	Too late
Do you have children?	No	Observed values	40	178	198
		Expected values	39.3	224.1	152.6
	Yes	Observed values	20	164	35
		Expected values	20.7	117.9	80.4

Table 7. Differences between males and females in experiencing anger because of official announcements and rules.

		Do the official announcements and rules anger you in any way?	
		No	Yes
Men	Observed values	137	99
	Expected values	122.3	113.7
Women	Observed values	192	207
	Expected values	206.7	192.3

Significantly more people aged 28 to 35 than expected compared with other age groups were angered by official announcements and rules during the coronavirus pandemic (χ^2 (N = 635; df = 3) = 37.519; $p < 0.001$; Cramer's $V = 0.243$, indicating a small effect size or medium effect size according to another interpretation).

Table 8. Differences between age groups on experiencing anger because of official announcements and rules.

			Do the official announcements and rules anger you in any way?	
			No	Yes
Age groups	20–23	Observed values	109	80
		Expected values	97.9	91.1
	24–27	Observed values	82	57
		Expected values	72.0	67.0
	28–35	Observed values	45	105
		Expected values	77.7	72.3
	36–65	Observed values	93	64
		Expected values	81.3	75.7

225 Bulgarians (35.4%) are inclined to blame someone for the current situation in Bulgaria, with some of those surveyed specifying their accusations against the government (Bulgarian and Chinese), the government for slow and inadequate responses, the president and leaders of political parties for prioritizing business over the well-being of citizens; doctors, pharmaceutical companies and scientists for their inability to cope; foreign arrivals who spread the plague; a global conspiracy to destroy old people. 410 Bulgarians (64.6%) do not think anyone is to blame for the coronavirus situation in Bulgaria.

Significantly more women than expected than men tend to blame someone for the current situation in Bul-

garia (χ^2 (N = 635; df = 1) = 5.470; p = 0.019; Cramer's V = 0.093, indicating a small effect size.

Table 9. Gender differences in the propensity to blame the current coronavirus situation in Bulgaria.

		Do you think someone is to blame for the current situation in Bulgaria?	
		No	Yes
Men	Observed values	166	70
	Expected values	152.4	83.6
Women	Observed values	244	155
	Expected values	257.6	141.4

These results reveal that the majority of surveyed Bulgarians (64.5% average percentage of indicators of trust in official authorities) experience psychosocial well-being in the form of trust in the information provided by official authorities during the coronavirus pandemic and in the measures taken and actions of the authorities related to social isolation, and when summarizing the socio-demographic differences, it was found that Bulgarians in the 36–65 age group seem to show the strongest trust. Approximately 1/3 of the surveyed Bulgarians (35.5% average percentage of indicators of trust in the official authorities) experience psychosocial distress in the form of mistrust in the information provided by the official authorities during the coronavirus pandemic and in the measures and actions taken by the authorities, associated with social isolation, and this mistrust is also associated with negative emotionality such as anger and attribution of blame. When summarizing the socio-demographic differences, it was found that Bulgarians between the ages of 28 and 35 show the strongest mistrust towards the official authorities, and mostly single people without an intimate partner and children, experience the greatest psychosocial distress under the form of mistrust towards the official authorities – towards the information provided by them and the measures taken by them to prevent the spread of coronavirus infection. Accordingly, people from the other

age groups with an intimate partner and children experience a more pronounced psycho-social well-being in the form of trust in the official authorities - in the information provided by them and the measures taken by them to prevent the spread of coronavirus infection.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Funding

No funding was reported.

Author contributions

All authors have contributed equally.

Author ORCIDs

Tsvetelina Mihaylova <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9238-2338>

Tsvetomir Dimitrov <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5493-6539>

Anton Koychev <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7855-5140>

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

References

- Angelova N (2020a) Review of the book "Psycho-social aspects of nutrition and eating disorders" written by Tsvetelina Hadzhieva. *Psychological Thought* 13(2): 491–495. <https://doi.org/10.37708/psyc.v13i2.538>
- Angelova N (2020b) Age and gender-related differences in money beliefs and attitudes. *Psychological Thought* 13(1): 169–204. <https://doi.org/10.37708/psyc.v13i1.404>
- Argyle M, Henderson M (1989) *Anatomiya na choveshkite otnosheniya* [Anatomy of human relationships]. Nauka i Izkustvo, Sofia, 368 pp. [In Bulgarian]
- Brito JA, Sampaio LS, Lessa RS, Vilela ABA, Santos LA, Silva JOL, Barreto PPM, Sampaio TSO (2019) Financial income and life satisfaction of the elderly intergenerational relations. *International Journal of Advanced Engineering Research and Science* 6(12): 220–225. <https://doi.org/10.22161/ijaers.612.18>
- Bryuhov VYu (2016) *Vzaimoponimanie uchastnikov pary i ikh predstavlenie o semeinoy zhizni* [Mutual understanding of partners and their ideas about family life]. Master's Thesis, Siberian Federal University, Krasnoyarsk, Russia. [In Russian]
- Chekhlaty EI (2006) *Issledovanie koping-mekhanizmov u studentov vuzov v svyazi s zadachami pervichnoy psikhigieny i psikhoprofylaktiki* [Investigation of coping mechanisms among university students for primary mental hygiene and prevention]. *Obozrenie psikhologii i meditsinskoy psikhologii imeni V.M. Bekhtereva* 2006(2). [In Russian]
- Chen CHV, Wang SJ, Chang WC, Hu CS (2008) The effect of leader-member exchange, trust, and supervisor support on organizational citizenship behaviour in nurses. *Journal of Nursing Research* 16(4): 321–328. <https://doi.org/10.1097/01.jnr.0000387319.28010.5e>
- Cohrs JC, Abele AE, Dette DE (2006) Integrating situational and dispositional determinants of job satisfaction: Findings from three samples

- of professionals. *Journal of Psychology: Interdisciplinary and Applied* 140(4): 363–395. <https://doi.org/10.3200/JRLP.140.4.363-395>
- Diener E, Gohm CL, Suh E, Oishi S (2000) Similarity of the relations between marital status and subjective well-being across cultures. *Journal of Cross-Cultural Psychology* 31(4): 419–436. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022022100031004001>
- Diener E, Seligman MEP (2004) Beyond money: Toward an economy of well-being. *Psychological Science in the Public Interest* 5(1): 1–31. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0963-7214.2004.00501001.x>
- Diener E, Ryan K (2009) Subjective well-being: A general overview. *South African Journal of Psychology* 39(4): 391–406. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0081246309039004002>
- Dolan SL, Tzafrir SS, Baruch Y (2013) Testing the causal relationships between procedural justice, trust and organizational citizenship behaviour. <http://www.reims-ms.fr/agrh/docs/actes-agrh/pdf-des-actes/2005dolan-tzafrir054.pdf> [accessed 8 Oct 2013]
- Eurostat (2019a) Quality of life indicators – Measuring quality of life. https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Quality_of_life_indicators_-_measuring_quality_of_life [accessed 15 May 2020]
- Eurostat (2019b) Quality of life indicators – governance and basic rights. https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Quality_of_life_indicators_-_governance_and_basic_rights [accessed 15 May 2020]
- Furnham A (2013) Individualnite razlichiya na rabotnoto myasto: izsledvane i obyasnayavane [Individual differences at the workplace: Research and explanation]. Iztok-Zapad, Sofia, 512 pp. [In Bulgarian]
- Goev V (1996) Statisticheska obrabotka i analiz na informatsiyata ot sotsiologicheski, marketingovi i politicheski izsledvaniya sas SPSS [Statistical processing and analysis of information from sociological, marketing and political research with SPSS]. University Publishing House “Stopanstvo,” Sofia, 342 pp. [In Bulgarian]
- Heim E, Augustiny K, Blaser A, Schaffner L (1991) Berner Bewältigungsformen (BEFO): Handbuch [Bern coping forms: Manual]. Verlag Hans Huber, Göttingen, 124 pp. [In German]
- Heim E (1995) Coping-based intervention strategies. *Patient Education and Counselling* 26(1–3): 145–151. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0738-3991\(95\)00733-G](https://doi.org/10.1016/0738-3991(95)00733-G)
- Heim E, Valach L, Schaffner L (1997) Coping and psychosocial adaptation: Longitudinal effects over time and stages in breast cancer. *Psychosomatic Medicine* 59(4): 408–418. <https://doi.org/10.1097/00006842-199707000-00011>
- Institute for Population and Human Studies (2020) Stres i spravyane s nego v usloviya na razprostranyavashta se infektsiya ot koronavirus – II chast [Stress and coping during the spread of coronavirus infection – Part II]. Report, Institute for Population and Human Studies, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences. [In Bulgarian]
- Inter-Agency Standing Committee [IASC] [Reference Group for Mental Health and Psychosocial Support in Emergency Settings] (2020) Briefing note on addressing mental health and psychosocial aspects of COVID-19 outbreak – Version 1.1. <https://interagencystandingcommittee.org/system/files/2020-03/MHPSS%20COVID19%20Briefing%20Note%202020March%202020-English.pdf> [accessed 10 Apr 2020]
- Jing Y, Bond MH (2015) Sources for trusting most people: How national goals for socializing children promote the contributions made by trust of the in-group and the out-group to non-specific trust. *Journal of Cross-Cultural Psychology* 46(2): 191–210. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022022114557488>
- Kesebir P, Diener E (2008) In pursuit of happiness: Empirical answers to philosophical questions. *Perspectives on Psychological Science* 3(2): 117–125. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1745-6916.2008.00069.x>
- Keyes CLM (1998) Social well-being. *Social Psychology Quarterly* 61(2): 121–140. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2787065>
- Korostyleva LA (2001) Psikhologiya samorealizatsii lichnosti: Osnovnye sfery zhiznedeyatelnosti [Psychology of personality self-realization: Main life spheres]. Doctoral Dissertation, St Petersburg State University, St Petersburg, Russia. [In Russian]
- Krastev L (2006) Znachenie i sastavni elementi na parichnite predstavi [Meaning and components of money representations]. *Psihologicheska misal 1* (Winter): 122–138. [In Bulgarian]
- Kriviradeva B (2019) Udovletvorenost ot profesionalniya trud na uchitelite v obrazovatelni institutsii: Rezultati ot empirichno izsledvane [Job satisfaction of teachers in educational institutions: Empirical study results]. *Pedagogika* 91(2): 159–179. [In Bulgarian]
- Lencioni P (2013) Preodolyavane na pette osnovni slabosti pri rabotata v ekip [Overcoming the five dysfunctions of a team]. Iztok-Zapad, Sofia, 216 pp. [In Bulgarian]
- Luhmann M, Lucas RE, Eid M, Diener E (2013) The prospective effect of life satisfaction on life events. *Social Psychological and Personality Science* 4(1): 39–45. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1948550612440105>
- Lykes VA, Kimmelmeier M (2014) What predicts loneliness? Cultural difference between individualistic and collectivistic societies in Europe. *Journal of Cross-Cultural Psychology* 45(3): 468–490. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022022113509881>
- Martínez-Corts I, Boz M, Medina FJ, Benítez M, Munduate L (2011) Coping with interpersonal conflict at work in small business: The moderating role of supervisor and co-worker support. *Revista de Psicología del Trabajo y de las Organizaciones* 27(2): 117–129. <https://doi.org/10.5093/tr2011v27n2a4>
- Mayer RC, Davis JH, Schoorman FD (1995) An integrative model of organizational trust. *Academy of Management Review* 20(3): 709–734. <https://doi.org/10.2307/258792>
- Melekhin AI (2015) Vospriyatie i poznanie vremeni v pozhilom i starcheskom vozraste: Obzor zarubezhnykh issledovaniy [Perception and cognition of time in elderly and senile age: Review of foreign research]. *Sovremennaya zarubezhnaya psikhologiya* 4(2): 11–19. [In Russian] <https://doi.org/10.17759/jmfp.2015040202>
- Miteva SS (2013) Adaptivni strategii i samorealizatsiya na studenti [Adaptive strategies and self-realization of students]. PhD Thesis Abstract, South-West University “Neofit Rilski,” Blagoevgrad, Bulgaria. [In Bulgarian]
- Mizova B, Bakracheva M, Bakalova D (2014) Psihologichni aspekti na vrazkata medijni poslaniya i subektivno blagopoluchie [Psychological aspects of the relationship between media messages and subjective well-being]. *Psihologichni izsledvaniya* 18(2): 517–524. [In Bulgarian]
- Montani F, Odoardi C, Battistelli A (2012) Explaining the relationships among supervisor support, affective commitment to change, and innovative work: The moderating role of coworker support. *Bollettino di Psicologia Applicata* 264: 43–57.
- Myers DG, Diener E (1995) Who is happy? *Psychological Science* 6(1): 10–19. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9280.1995.tb00298.x>
- Myers DG (2000) Sotsial'naya psikhologiya [Social psychology]. Piter, Saint Petersburg, 784 pp. [In Russian]
- NHS Health Scotland (2008) Review of scales of positive mental health validated for use with adults in the UK: Technical report December 2007. Health Scotland, Edinburgh, 73 pp. <http://www.healthscotland.gov.uk/>

- scot/media/2244/review-of-scales-of-positive-mental-health-validated-for-use-with-adults-in-the-uk.pdf [accessed May 2020]
- Nikolova M, Nikolaev B (2016) Does joining the EU make you happy? Evidence from Bulgaria and Romania. IZA Discussion Paper 9636, Institute of Labor Economics (IZA), Bonn. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2716577> [accessed 10 Aug 2018]
- Oddagipermarket (2019) Prevenziya na sindroma na izgaryane sred sluzhitelite: Profesionalna deformatsiya i emocionalno izgaryane na sluzhitelite [Prevention of employee burnout: Professional deformation and emotional burnout among prison staff]. <https://oddagipermarket.ru/bg/nalogi-i-platezhi/profilaktika-sindroma-emocionalno-go-vygoraniya-u-sotrudnikov-uis.html> [accessed May 2020]
- Psycabi.net (2020a) Vychod iz slozhnykh situatsii. Diagnostika kopiyng strategij Hajma (Test Hajma bor'by so stressom) [Finding a way out of difficult situations: Haim's coping strategies diagnostic]. <https://psycabi.net/testy/178-ishchem-vychod-iz-slozhnykh-situatsij-metodika-dlya-psikhologicheskoy-diagnostiki-kopiyng-mekhanizmov-test-khajma> [accessed 15 Apr 2020]
- Psycabi.net (2020b) Risunochnyj test na doverie, proektivnye metodiki [Drawing test of trust, projective methods]. <https://psycabi.net/testy/447-risunochnyj-test-na-doverie-proektivnye-metodiki> [accessed April 2020]
- Radoslavova M, Velichkov A (2005) Metodi za psihodiagnostika [Methods for psychodiagnostics]. Pandora Prim, Sofia, 285 pp. [In Bulgarian]
- Rusinova-Hristova A, Karastoyanov G (2000) Psikhologichnite tipove po Karl Jung i stresat [Carl Jung's psychological types and stress]. Propeler, Sofia, 212 pp. [In Bulgarian]
- Schmid G (1997) Krankenseelsorge im Kontext interdisziplinärer Bewältigungshilfe [Health care in the context of interdisciplinary coping aid]. *Theologie und Glaube* 87: 112–130. [In German]
- Selye H (1982) Stres bez distres [Stress without distress]. Transl. V Tsvetkov. Nauka i Izkustvo, Sofia, 312 pp. [In Bulgarian]
- Shaimuhametova SF (2010) Psikhicheskie sostoyaniya suprugov na raznykh etapakh razvitiya sem'i [Mental states of spouses at different stages of family development]. PhD Thesis Abstract, Kazan State University, Kazan, Russia. [In Russian]
- Sheeba J, Manimegalai T, Akila K (2018) A study on job satisfaction towards IT employees in Coimbatore. *International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development* 2(3): 393–397. <https://doi.org/10.31142/ijtsrd10821>
- Spitzmuller M, Van Dyne L, Ilies R (2008) Organizational citizenship behaviour: A review and extension of its nomological network. In: Barling J, Cooper CL (Eds) *The SAGE Handbook of Organizational Behaviour*. Sage, Thousand Oaks, CA, 106–123. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781849200448.n7>
- Stamatov R, Minchev B (2003) Psikhologiya na choveka [Human psychology]. Hermes, Plovdiv, 744 pp. [In Bulgarian]
- Stanoeva G (2015) Mezhdulichnostni otnosheniya na rabotnoto myasto v sferata na humanitarni i tehnicneski professii [Interpersonal relationships at the workplace in humanitarian and technical professions]. PhD Thesis Abstract, South-West University "Neofit Rilski," Blagoevgrad, Bulgaria. [In Bulgarian]
- Stefanova-Bakracheva M (2006) Statusi na identichnost i intimnost [Identity and intimacy statuses]. *Psihologicheska misal* 1 (Summer): 91–103. [In Bulgarian]
- Stofur D (2005) Obshtuvaneto v neednorodni i virtualni ekipi [Communication in heterogeneous and virtual teams]. In: *Idealniyat ekip, koito raboti kato chasovnikov mehanizam* [The ideal team that works like clockwork]. Lokus Publishing, Sofia, 85–104. [In Bulgarian]
- Tay L, Herian MN, Diener E (2014a) Corrigendum: Detrimental effects of corruption on subjective well-being: Whether, how, and when. *Social Psychological and Personality Science* 6(1): 117. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1948550614553221>
- Tay L, Herian MN, Diener E (2014b) Detrimental effects of corruption and subjective well-being: Whether, how, and when. *Social Psychological and Personality Science* 5(7): 751–759. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1948550614528544>
- Tolor A, Cramer M, D'Amico D, O'Marra MM (1975) The effects of self-concept, trust, and imagined positive or negative self-disclosures on psychological space. *Journal of Psychology* 89(1): 9–24. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00223980.1975.9923902>
- Uzunov NK (2000) Stres i psikhotravma: Mekhanizmi, bolesti, psikhoterapiya /nov pogled/ [Stress and psychotrauma: Mechanisms, diseases, psychotherapy / new perspective /]. *Znanie, Stara Zagora*, 240 pp. [In Bulgarian]
- Vinson T, Ericson M (2012) *Life satisfaction and happiness*. Jesuit Social Services, Richmond, 72 pp.
- Zankova KR (2015) Interaktivni efekti na protektivnite lichnostni resursi i depresivnata simptomatika varhu psichichnoto zdrave [Interactive effects of protective personality resources and depressive symptoms on mental health]. PhD Thesis Abstract, Sofia University "St Kliment Ohridski," Sofia. [In Bulgarian]
- Zhang AY, Tsui AS, Song LJ, Li C, Jia L (2008) How do I trust thee? The employee–organization relationship, supervisory support, and middle-manager trust in the organization. *Human Resource Management* 47(1): 111–132. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hrm.20200>